

Diversity, spatial and temporal distribution of above-ground arthropods associated with watermelon in the Nigerian southern guinea savanna

Okrikata Emmanuel^{1*}, Ogunwolu Emmanuel Oludele² and Ukwela Monday Unwabunne²

¹ Department of Biological Sciences, Federal University Wukari, Taraba State, Nigeria.

² Department of Crop and Environmental Protection, Federal University of Agriculture, Makurdi, Benue State, Nigeria.

ABSTRACT. Arthropods were sampled on an early- and late-season crop of watermelon in the 2016 cropping season using motorized suction sampler swept along 5m length of the middle row of 20 experimental plots at Federal University Wukari. Specimens were sorted to morphotypes, feeding guilds and as dominant based on percentage relative abundance (RA) and frequency of occurrence (FO). Different species diversity indices were computed. The collections made on the early- and late-sown crops were compared using Jaccard's Similarity index (C_j). Spatial distribution pattern of the dominant arthropods were determined using Taylor's power law and Iwao's patchiness regression. Results showed that collections on both crops were similar ($C_j = 0.83$). A total of 14,466 specimens sorted to 1 order (Araneae) in the class Arachnida and 64 species in 41 families and 8 orders in the class Hexapoda were collected. Data showed moderately high species diversity ($H = 2.8-3.0$), richness ($R = 6.0-7.2$), but low evenness ($E = 0.26-0.39$). Coleopterous insects (22 species), dominated by chrysomelids, were the most diverse and species-rich followed by hymenopterans, mainly formicids. Dominant arthropods ($RA \geq 1.0$ and $FO \geq 25.0\%$) included *Asbecesta nigripennis*, *Aulacophora africana*, *Philanthus triangulum* (parasitoid of bee), *Pheidole* sp., *Camponotus* sp., *Rhynocoris nitidulus* and spiders. Most dominant arthropods were aggregated; dispersion varied with model used and crop season. Only 27.3% of the diverse and rich arthropods on watermelon at Wukari require pest management intervention and validation of their dispersion pattern in large-scale watermelon production.

Key words: Buzas and Gibson's Evenness, Iwao's patchiness regression, Shannon-Weiner index, Taylor's power law, Variance to mean ratio

Received:
25 January, 2019

Accepted:
02 March, 2019

Published:
11 March, 2019

Subject Editor:
Ali Asghar Talebi

Citation: Emmanuel, O., Emmanuel Oludele, O. & Monday Unwabunne, U. (2019) Diversity, spatial and temporal distribution of above-ground arthropods associated with watermelon in the Nigerian southern guinea savanna. *Journal of Insect Biodiversity and Systematics*, 5 (1), 11–32.

Introduction

Watermelon, *Citrullus lanatus* Thunb. (Cucurbitaceae), accounts for 6.8% of the world area devoted to vegetable production (Goreta et al., 2005; Gichimu et

al., 2008) and its global consumption is greater than that of any other cucurbit. The crop is gaining a foothold in fruit-based food production across diverse agro-

Corresponding author: Okrikata Emmanuel, E-mail: eokrikata@gmail.com

Copyright © 2019, Emmanuel et al. This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (CC BY 4.0), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

ecological zones of Nigeria driven by its nutritional, health, and profitable returns to production and marketing investments (Perkins-Veazie & Collins, 2004; Sabo et al., 2013; Ajewole, 2015; Alao & Adebayo, 2015, Okrikata et al., 2019). Economic incentive is fueling proclivity for year-round production with the consequence of organization and stabilization of a community structure of diverse animals. Knowledge of the diversity and richness of organisms in the community is vital to identification of negatively-impacting pest species, the dynamics of their populations, the concomitant effective pest management and safe guarding of human and environmental health as well as to detection of new species, and the rates of species extinction in the habitat (Sisk et al., 1994; Humphries et al., 1995; Mirab-balou et al., 2017).

Entomofaunal studies in watermelon producing areas in Nigeria (Ogunlana, 1996; Bamaiyi et al., 2010; Burabai et al., 2011; Alao and Adebayo, 2015; Malik et al., 2015) had been purposively for pest identification and control. Hardly did any focus on species diversity, richness and dispersion of pest and beneficial organisms. Spatial distribution is an important ecological attribute of arthropod populations and a behavioral response of individuals of a species to the interactions of the complex biological and environmental factors in a given habitat (Sevacherian & Stern, 1972; Steffy, 1979; Arbab & Bakry, 2016). The spatial structure of arthropod populations differs among species (Soemargono et al., 2011); it is influenced by resource availability (Pedigo & Buntin, 1994) and it is important in developing efficient and precise field sampling programs, field monitoring plans, density estimation strategies, population models and ultimately pest management decisions (Khaing et al., 2002; Arbab & Backry, 2016). In this paper, we provide a comprehensive

list of the guilds of insects infesting watermelon, their diversity, richness and evenness at a Southern Guinea Savanna location in Nigeria.

Material and methods

Location and study design

The study was conducted at teaching and research farm of Federal University Wukari, Taraba State, Nigeria (Latitude 7° 51' N and Longitude 9° 47' E) characterized by warm tropical climate with distinct wet and dry seasons, an annual average temperature of 26.8°C and 1205 mm of rainfall. The crop was established from treated seeds of Kaolack variety of watermelon spaced 1 m within a row and 2 m between rows of plots that were 5 m long and 8 m wide during the early- and late- cropping season of 2016. The plots were hoe-weeded and soil nutrient supplemented with NPK (15:15:15) fertilizer applied at the rate of 200kg/ha.

Sampling of arthropod species commenced at 70 % emergence stage [2 weeks after planting (WAP)] and proceeded at weekly intervals until fruit maturity. A motorized suction sampler with 10 cm diameter inlet cone was used to collect arthropods on plants along the 5 m length of the middle row of each plot (at an approximate walking speed of 1 m/second ≈5 seconds/5 m middle-row/plot) between 1600 and 1800 h. However, to ensure effective sampling of pollinators, collections were made between 0700 and 0900 h during the flowering stage of the crop. Visual observation complemented suction sampling.

Before suction sampling, plants were visually examined to document the parts attacked by dominant insect pests as well as the insects attacked by natural enemies. The specimens collected were killed in ethyl acetate and transported in labeled bags to the laboratory for sorting; the

immature stages were reared to adult stage in the laboratory on appropriate food resource. While butterflies and moths were mounted on pins, dried and kept in air-tight boxes containing silica gel, other arthropods were preserved in 70 % ethanol. Insects were identified to species at the Insect Museum of Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, and then grouped into feeding guilds (Wardhaugh et al., 2012).

Data analysis

The diversity and number of arthropod taxa/species and orders collected and their frequency of occurrence (FO) and relative abundance (RA) were computed for both the early-and late-sown crops. Taxa/species with FO ≥ 25 % and RA ≥ 1 % were regarded as dominant while, those with FO < 25 % and/or, RA < 1 % were regarded as rare following the scale outlined by Zaime & Gautier (1989) and Dajoz (2000) cited in Adja et al. (2016) and Ajayi et al. (2018). The dominant taxa/species were used to compute the natural enemies to pests' ratio (calculated as the sum of natural enemies divided by sum of the pests) for both the early- and late-sown crops. Temporal spread and weekly fluctuations of dominant arthropods were graphically illustrated.

Diversity indices (Shannon-Weiner diversity index, Margalef's species richness index and, Buzas and Gibson's Evenness index) were computed using the Paleontological Statistical Tool -Past₃ (Hammer et al., 2001). Similarity between the arthropod taxa collected on the early- and late-sown crops was computed using the Jaccard's similarity index (Ogbeibu, 2014);

Shannon index (H) = $-\sum P_i \times \ln(P_i)$

Where;

$P_i = n/N$

n = Number of individuals of one species

N = Total number of all individuals in the sample

ln = Natural logarithm

Margalef's Richness (R) = $(S-1)/\ln(n)$

Where;

S = Number of species

n = Number of individuals

ln = Natural logarithm

Buzas and Gibson's Evenness (E) = e^H/S

Where;

e = Natural logarithm base

H = Shannon index

S = Number of species

Jaccard's index (C_j) = $a/a+b+c$

Where;

a - No. of taxa/species found on both the early and late sown crops

b - No. of taxa/species found on early and not on late sown crops

c - No. of taxa/species found on the late and not on the early sown crops

Dispersion indices

The variance to mean ratio (S^2/m) proposed by Myers, 1978 in which $S^2/m = 1, <1$ and >1 indicates random, regular and aggregated dispersion, respectively was used to form a tentative opinion on dispersion patterns of the dominant arthropod taxa/species. It was computed in relation to the stages of growth of the crop.

Linear regression models

Taylor's power law states that the variance (S^2) of a population is proportional to the fractional power of the arithmetic mean (m): $S^2 = am^b$.

To estimate a and b , the values of $\log(S^2)$ were regressed against $\log(m)$ using the formula;

$\log(S^2) = \log(a) + b \log(m)$

Where the intercept (a) is the sampling/computing factor which changes with sampling unit and, the slope (b) is an index of aggregation that indicates a uniform, random or aggregated dispersion when $b < 1$, $= 1$ or > 1 , respectively (Southwood, 1978).

The Iwao's patchiness regression method quantifies the relationship between the mean crowding (m^*) and the mean (m) using the formula;

$$m^* = \alpha + \beta m$$

Where m^* is the mean crowding (Lloyd, 1967). The intercept (α) is the index of basic contagion of a population.

Where;

$\alpha = 0$ [the basic unit of a population is a single individual (a tendency to random dispersion)].

$\alpha > 0$ [there is a positive association between individuals (a tendency to aggregated dispersion)].

$\alpha < 0$ [there is a negative/repulsive association between individuals (a tendency to regular dispersion)].

The slope (β) is the density contagiousness coefficient interpreted in the same manner as b of Taylor's regression both of which were computed at 95 % confidence interval (Iwao & Kuno, 1968).

Results

Diversity, abundance and dispersion of arthropods on watermelon

A total of 14,466 specimens sorted into 1 order (Araneae) of the class Arachnida and into 64 species in 41 families and 8 orders of the class Insecta for the early-sown crop and 1 order (Araneae), 53 species in 36 families and 8 orders of insects for the late-sown crop were collected (Tables 1, 2 and 3). Colonization of the early- and late-sown crops was comparable (Jaccard's Similarity Index=0.83). The results show moderately high species diversity (Shannon-Wiener's

Index of 2.8–3.0), species richness (Margalef's Richness Index of 6.0–7.2), but low evenness (Buzas and Gibson's Evenness Index of 0.26–0.39) of the arthropods (Table 2).

The insect order Coleoptera was the most diverse (22 species) and numerically dominant with members of the family Chrysomelidae (RA = 8.02–16.04 %, FO = 45.56–80.0 %) being highly abundant and species-rich. Next was the order Hymenoptera (10 species) with members of the family Formicidae (RA = 1.43–6.55%, FO = 27.78–65.00 %) being most abundant and species-rich (Table 3). Coleopterous insects were 4x more abundant than hymenopterans on the early-sown crop but on the late-sown crop the magnitude of difference was 2.2-fold. However, the former order had the lowest species evenness value.

The dominant arthropod species (RA \geq 1.0 % and FO \geq 25.0 %) included *Asbecesta nigripennis* Weise, *A. transversa* Allard, *Aulacophora africana* Weise, *Monolepta nigeriae* Bryant, *Epilachna chrysomelina* Fab, *Bemisia tabaci* Genn., *Aphis gossypii* Glove., *Bactrocera cucurbitae* Coq., *Heliiothis armigera* Hub., *Cheilomenes sulphurea* Oliv., *Philanthus triangulum* Fab., *Apis mellifera* L., *Crematogaster* sp., *Pheidole* sp., *Camponotus* sp., *Cardiochiles niger* H. & W., *Rhynocoris nitidulus* Fab., and spiders. All others (72.3 % of the collection) were rare or scarce (RA $<$ 1.0 % and/or FO $<$ 25.0 %).

Five feeding guilds were recognized: herbivores (26 taxa), carnivores comprising 17 taxa of predators and 6 taxa of parasitoids, detritivores (6 taxa), pollinators (3 taxa), multi-category and opportunistic feeders (7 taxa). The dominant herbivores constituted 62.6–68.5 % of the collections compared with 15.1–23.4 % for the dominant carnivores giving on the average a ratio of 0.3 carnivore to 1 herbivore. *Apis mellifera* was the main pollinator species (Table 4).

Table 1. Diversity, richness, and evenness of the taxa collected on watermelon at Wukari in 2016 Cropping Season.

Arachnid/ insect order	Early-sown					Late-sown				
	S ¹	N ²	H ³	R ⁴	E ⁵	S	N	H	R	E
Araneae*	1	86	0.000	0.000	1	1	79	0.000	0.000	1
Blattodea	2	28	0.257	0.300	0.647	1	39	0.000	0.000	1
Coleoptera	22	5195	1.867	2.445	0.294	19	3500	1.879	2.206	0.345
Diptera	8	280	1.149	1.242	0.395	4	232	0.726	0.551	0.517
Hemiptera	8	482	1.46	1.385	0.539	7	996	1.305	0.869	0.527
Hymenoptera	10	1288	1.832	1.257	0.624	10	1557	1.804	1.224	0.607
Lepidoptera	5	81	1.517	0.910	0.912	5	373	0.894	0.676	0.489
Mantodea	2	49	0.688	0.257	0.995	2	42	0.675	0.268	0.982
Orthoptera	7	76	1.804	1.385	0.868	5	83	1.558	0.905	0.950

* All species of spiders were treated as a taxon; ¹S Number of species; ²N Number of individuals/specimens; ³H Shannon-Weiner diversity index; ⁴R Margalef's species richness index; ⁵E Buzas and Gibson's evenness.

Table 2. Diversity indices of arthropods collected from watermelon field plots at Wukari in 2016 Cropping Season.

Diversity indices	Early-sown ¹	Late-sown ²	Inference
Shannon-Weiner Index (H)	2.825	3.040	High species diversity
Margalef's Richness Index (R)	7.166	5.996	Species richness is high. Higher on the early than late-sown crop
Buzas and Gibson's Evenness Index (E)	0.259	0.387	Even distribution of individuals among species is low/few sampled species dominates
Jaccard's Similarity Index (C _j)		0.83	Similarity of species is high between early and late-sown crops

¹ 7565 arthropods in 65 species were collected; ² 6901 arthropods in 54 species were collected.

Table 3. Relative abundance and frequency of occurrence of arthropod specimens collected on watermelon at Wukari in 2016 cropping season.

Arachnid/ insect order	Family	Species	Early-sown		Late-sown	
			FO (%) ¹	RA (%) ²	FO (%) ¹	RA (%) ²
Araneae		Spiders*	30.00	1.14	31.11	1.14
Blattodea	Blaberidae	<i>Gyna costalis</i> Walker	1.11	0.03	-	-
	Termitidae	<i>Odontotermes</i> sp.	4.44	0.34	9.44	0.57
Coleoptera	Carabidae	<i>Cicindela melancholica</i> F.	5.00	0.16	3.89	0.13
		<i>Megacephala denticollis</i> Chd.	2.78	0.08	1.67	0.06
		<i>Platymetopus vestitus</i> Dej.	3.33	0.20	3.89	0.26
	Cerambycidae	<i>Derobrachus geminatus</i> Leconte	1.11	0.07	1.67	0.07
	Chrysomelidae	<i>Asbecesta nigripennis</i> Weise	80.00	16.04	66.22	14.24
		<i>Asbecesta transversa</i> Allard	75.56	12.86	51.11	8.47
		<i>Aulacophora africana</i> Weise	60.56	12.70	45.56	8.02
		<i>Monolepta nigeriae</i> Bryant	68.89	13.82	55.56	10.50
	Coccinellidae	<i>Cheilomenes sulphurea</i> Oliv.	40.56	4.37	50.00	3.87
		<i>Epilachna chrysomelina</i> Fab.	67.22	6.91	43.89	3.62
		<i>Exochomus flavipes</i> Thunb.	8.89	0.49	9.44	0.45
	Curculionidae	<i>Diaecoderus</i> sp.	1.67	0.07	1.11	0.03
		<i>Omotrachelus togoanus</i> Mshl.	2.78	0.13	2.78	0.14
	Lycidae	<i>Lycus corniger</i> Dalm.	1.11	0.04	1.67	0.07
Nitidulidae	<i>Carpophilus dimidiatus</i> F.	1.67	0.16	2.22	0.19	
Passandridae	<i>Hectarthrum heros</i> Fab.	1.67	0.11	2.22	0.14	
Scarabaeidae	<i>Aulacoserica</i> sp.	1.11	0.04	-	-	
	<i>Copris megaceratoides</i> Waterhouse	5.00	0.20	3.89	0.23	

Table 3. Continued

Arachnid/ insect order	Family	Species	Early-sown		Late-sown	
			FO (%) ¹	RA (%) ²	FO (%) ¹	RA (%) ²
		<i>Heteronychus mossambicus</i> Couple	3.33	0.11	2.78	0.10
		<i>Onthophagus vinctus</i> Er.	2.22	0.09	3.33	0.13
	Tenebrionidae	<i>Cossyphus senegalensis</i> Cast.	0.56	0.01	-	-
		<i>Phrynocolus dentatus</i> Sol.	1.11	0.03	-	-
Diptera	Asilidae	<i>Laxenecera albicincta</i> Loen.	4.44	0.26	2.78	0.22
	Drosophilidae	<i>Zaprionus indianus</i> Gupta	3.89	0.16	-	-
	Hippoboscidae	<i>Pseudolynchia canariensis</i> Macq.	1.11	0.03	-	-
	Muscidae	<i>Lispe leucospila</i> Wied.	3.33	0.19	-	-
	Muscidae	<i>Morellia prolectata</i> Walk.	1.67	0.11	-	-
		<i>Musca domestica</i> L.	2.78	0.16	3.89	0.23
	Syrphididae	<i>Phytomia incisa</i> Wied.	4.44	0.20	3.89	0.23
	Tephritidae	<i>Bactrocera cucurbitae</i> Coq.	43.89	2.60	33.89	2.74
Hemiptera	Aleyrodidae	<i>Bemisia tabaci</i> Genn.	36.11	1.67	46.11	4.98
	Aphididae	<i>Aphis craccivora</i> Kock.	2.78	0.23	7.22	0.46
		<i>Aphis gossypii</i> Glove.	38.33	1.88	43.33	5.97
	Aphrophoridae	<i>Poophilus costalis</i> Walker	1.67	0.04	1.11	0.03
	Cicadidae	<i>Trismarcha</i> sp.	0.56	0.01	-	-
	Pentatomidae	<i>Aspavia acuminata</i> Mont.	3.89	0.21	3.89	0.20
	Pyrrhocoridae	<i>Odontopus nigricornis</i> Stal.	3.33	0.19	6.11	0.34
	Reduviidae	<i>Rhynocoris nitidulus</i> Fab.	25.56	2.15	23.89	2.43
Hymenoptera	Apidae	<i>Apis mellifera</i> L.	38.33	4.86	30.56	5.87
	Braconidae	<i>Apanteles syleptae</i> Fer.	4.44	0.20	1.67	0.22

Table 3. Continued

Arachnid/ insect order	Family	Species	Early-sown		Late-sown	
			FO (%) ¹	RA (%) ²	FO (%) ¹	RA (%) ²
		<i>Cardiochiles niger</i> H. & W.	30.00	2.06	38.88	2.77
	Chrysididae	<i>Chrysis convexifrons</i> Mocs.	2.78	0.12	2.78	0.17
	Crabronidae	<i>Philanthus triangulum</i> Fab.	36.11	2.21	36.11	2.04
	Formicidae	<i>Camponotus</i> sp.	36.11	1.43	36.11	2.09
		<i>Crematogaster</i> sp.	27.78	1.45	35.00	2.46
		<i>Pheidole</i> sp.	58.33	4.29	65.00	6.55
	Ichneumonidae	<i>Goryphus bunoh</i> Guald	2.22	0.12	3.33	0.12
	Vespidae	<i>Polistes spilophorus</i> Schlett.	2.78	0.24	5.56	0.22
Lepidoptera	Arctiidae	<i>Cretonotus leucaniodes</i> Holland	3.89	0.24	8.33	0.23
	Lycaenidae	<i>Zizeeria</i> sp.	3.89	0.21	4.44	0.29
	Noctuidae	<i>Heliothis armigera</i> Hub.	2.22	0.08	41.46	4.07
	Nymphalidae	<i>Acraea eponina</i> Cr.	5.00	0.36	6.67	0.41
Lepidoptera	Thyrididae	<i>Epaena danista</i> Whalley	2.78	0.19	4.44	0.75
Mantodea	Mantidae	<i>Elaea</i> sp.	3.89	0.29	4.44	0.25
		<i>Miomantis</i> sp.	4.44	0.36	5.56	0.36
Orthoptera	Acrididae	<i>Gastrimargus amplus</i> Sjost.	2.22	0.09	-	-
		<i>Oedaleus nigeriensis</i> Ovarov	6.67	0.29	6.11	
	Gryllidae	<i>Acanthoplistus</i> sp.	2.22	0.09	4.44	0.26
		<i>Brachytrupes membranaceus</i> Dry.	1.11	0.07	-	-
		<i>Gymnogryllus</i> sp.	1.11	0.08	3.89	0.19
	Pyrgomorphidae	<i>Atractomorpha acutipennis</i> Guer.	3.33	0.22	5.00	0.23
<i>Pyrrgomorpha</i> sp.		3.89	0.16	4.44	0.14	

* Jaccard's similarity index = 0.83; ** Spider species were treated as a single taxon; ¹ FO - Frequency of occurrence; ² RA - Relative abundance.

Table 4. Feeding guilds of the dominant arthropods collected on watermelon at Wukari in 2016 cropping season.

Guild*	Species**	Plant part attacked***	Host/prey
Hb	<i>A. africana</i>	Le, Fl, Fr	
	<i>A. gossypii</i>	Le, Vi, Fr	
	<i>A. nigripennis</i>	Le, Fl, Fr	
	<i>A. transversa</i>	Le, Fl, Fr	
	<i>B. tabaci</i>	Le, Vi, Fr	
	<i>E. chrysomelina</i>	Le, Fl, Fr	
	<i>H. armigera</i>	Le, Fl, Fr	
	<i>M. nigeriae</i>	Le, Fl, Fr	
Hb/P	<i>B. cucurbitae</i>	Fl, Fr	
o			
Po	<i>A. mellifera</i>	—	—
Pa	<i>C. niger</i>		Larvae of beetles, flies and lepidopterans ¹
	<i>P. triangulum</i>		Bees ²
Pr	<i>C. sulphurea</i>		Mites, aphids/Soft bodied insects ³
	Predatory ants ⁺		Aphids, lepidopterous larvae, beetles, termites ^{4, 5, 6}
	<i>R. nitidulus</i>		Polyphagous ⁷
	Spiders		Polyphagous ⁸

* Hb – Herbivore (include defoliators, sap suckers, flower and fruit feeders)

Pr – Predator

Pa – Parasitoid

Po – Pollinator

** Arthropod taxa with frequency of occurrence ≥ 25.0 % and relative abundance ≥ 1.0 %.

*** Le – Leaf; Fl – Flower; Fr – Fruit; Vi – Vine

+ *Camponotus* sp., *Crematogaster* sp., *Pheidole* sp.

¹. Adja et al., 2016, ². Gess & Gess, 2014, ³. Mrosso et al., 2013, ⁴. Richard et al., 2001, ⁵. Oliveira et al., 2012, ⁶. El Keroumi et al., 2010, ⁷. Subramanian & Kitherian, 2012, ⁸. Riechert & Lawrence, 1997.

Infestation of the leaf-feeding beetles commenced at the seedling stage and traversed to the fruiting stage; the density peaked at 6 - 7 WAP in the early- and at 5 WAP in the late-sown crop (Figs 1A, B; 2A, B). Among sap-sucking insects, *B. tabaci*

was the early colonizer (2 and 4 WAP the early- and late-sown crop, respectively), followed by *A. gossypii* (4 and 3 WAP the early- and late-sown crop, respectively) [Figs 1A, B]. Their infestation persisted to the fruiting stage. The leaf-eating beetles

generally occurred at a higher density in the early- than late-sown crop. The reverse was observed with respect to the sap-sucking insects (Figs 2A, B). *Heliothis armigera* was scarce in the early-sown crop but in the late-sown crop infestation commenced at 4 WAP and spanned the fruiting duration. At peak density, there were 3.6 larvae/5 m length of row (Figs 1B, 2B). The fruit fly, *B. cucurbitae*, and bees (*A. mellifera*) colonized the crop at the onset of flowering and persisted through to fruiting stage. Density of the former peaked at 2.7 and 2.0/5 m length of row on the early- and late-sown crop, respectively, while that of the latter peaked at 4.7/5 m and 6.2/5 m length of row on the early- and late-sown crop, respectively (Figs 1A, B; 2A, B). Infestation by ants collectively straddled entire crop growth duration attaining peaks at 6 and 4 WAP in the early- and late-sown crop, respectively (Figs 1A,B; 3A, B). Spiders followed a similar trend but had a bimodal peak on the early crop (4 and 9 WAP) and a single peak (7 WAP) on the late-sown crop (Figs 3A, B).

On the average, densities of pests and beneficial arthropods progressively increased with crop growth attaining a peak at flowering and declining at fruiting stage (Tables 5, 6). Pest density declined 2 weeks earlier on the late- than on the early-sown crop. Beneficial arthropods attained peak density much earlier on the late- than on the early-sown crop. Average density of beetles, predominantly *A. nigripennis*, *A. africana*, and *M. nigeriae*, exceeded the densities of sap-sucking and fruit-feeding insects except on the late-sown crop where average density of *A. gossypii* and *B. tabaci* was higher. Among the beneficial insects, *A. mellifera* had the highest average density on the early-sown crop while on the late-sown crop, *Pheidole* sp. had the highest density.

Taylor's and Iwao's regression models' gave inconsistent dispersion patterns. *Rhynocoris nitidulus* was randomly dispersed using Taylor's model but it was aggregated using Iwao's model (early-sown). On the other hand, *C. sulphurea* was uniformly dispersed with Iwao's regression while it was aggregated with Taylor's regression model late-sown). *Epilachna chrysomelina* was uniformly dispersed on both crops (early- and late-sown). *A. gossypii* and *B. cucurbitae* which were uniformly dispersed on the early-sown crop had aggregated dispersion on the late-sown crop. In the opposite direction, *A. transversa* which were aggregated on the early-sown crop were uniformly dispersed on the late-sown crop (Tables 7, 8). With the same model, dispersion pattern occasionally differed. For example, *C. sulphurea* exhibited uniform dispersion on the early-sown crop but it was aggregated on the late-sown crop (Taylor's power law). *Rhynocoris nitidulus* was aggregated on the early-sown but randomly dispersed on the late-sown crop (Iwao's patchiness regression).

Discussion

The suction sampler has been shown to be efficient in extracting immature and small- to large-sized invertebrates from low vegetation and it gives unbiased density estimates (Grootaert et al., 2010). Though suction samplers have been shown to be less efficient than pitfall traps in collecting spiders and carabid beetles, reasonable success have been recorded in their use for spider and carabid sampling as also observed in the current study (Merrett, 1983; Gibson et al., 1992; Mommertz et al., 1996; Standen, 2000; Brook et al., 2008; McCravy, 2018).

Figure 1. Temporal spread of common arthropods associated with watermelon at Wukari in 2016 cropping season. A) early-sown crop. B) late-sown crop.

Figure 2. Weekly fluctuations in density of dominant insect pests collected on watermelon at Wukari in 2016 cropping season. A) early-sown crop. B) late-sown crop.

The use of suction sampler in this study accounts for the more comprehensive documentation of arthropods associated with watermelon than those of Ogunlana (1996), Bamaiyi et al. (2010), Burabai et al. (2011), Alao & Adebayo (2015), and Malik et al. (2015). This apart, the authors paid no attention to arthropods whose ecological functions in the community were flower pollination and pest density regulation.

Insect species previously documented but not sighted in this study include: *Copa occidentalis*, *Coccinella septempunctata*, *Diabrotica undecimpunctata*, *Ootheca mutabilis*, *Podagrica* spp., *Phyllotreta cruciferae* [Coleoptera]; *Dacus cucurbitae* [Diptera]; *Zonocerus variegatus* [Orthoptera]; and *Thrips palmi* [Thysanoptera]. Variations in species diversity by geographical location and agroclimatic conditions are

well known and reported (Umeozor, 1998; Alao et al., 2016).

Decision which takes no cognizance of the high proportion (72.3 %) of rare species (FO < 25 % and/or, RA < 1 %) which in this study include species belonging the family termitidae, carabidae, curculionidae, tenebrionidae and hippoboscidae etc. and the disproportionate density of carnivores to pest density in controlling pests with synthetic chemicals is bound to be unsustainable, inimical to the optimization of biological control, and negatively impactful on human and environmental health (Okrikata & Ogunwolu, 2017).

Similar to the findings of Tom & Kaippallil (2016), the insect order Coleoptera was the most abundant and diverse. The family Chrysomelidae had high representation probably as a result of co-evolution in which cucurbits' defensive chemical against insect predation equally serves as a chemical cue for host location by chrysomelid beetles of the tribe Luperini (Koul, 2008). In this study, pest infestation was season-long and based on their densities and temporal spread, *A. nigripennis*, *A. africana*, and *A. transversa* (leaf feeders); *A. gossypii*, and *B. tabaci* (sap-suckers); and *H. armigera*, and *B. cucurbitae* (fruit feeders) are classifiable as the key field pests of watermelon, a designation consistent with the reports by Bamaïyi et al. (2010), Lima et al. (2014), and Alao et al. (2016). *Bactrocera cucurbitae*, a pest of quarantine importance, occurred at a higher density than Malik et al. (2015) documented in their study at Zaria, Nigeria. Concerted effort must be made to curtail its spread and suppress its population in order to avoid restriction of export trading in this commodity. Observation of *A. mellifera*, ants, in particular *Pheidole* and *Crematogaster* sp., as key beneficial organisms in the community

confirms previous report by Lima et al. (2014). Given the dearth of research on spider species in Nigeria and especially in the study area, identification of spiders was difficult hence; the spider species collected in this study were treated as a taxon.

Differences found between planting dates for arthropod composition, relative abundance and diversity may relate to weather factors, suitability of host for feeding and oviposition, and density of naturally-occurring biotic agents (Pedigo & Buntin, 1994). Knowledge of pest density and temporal spread is indispensable for pest management decision making (Kumar, 1984). Appropriate and efficient pest sampling protocol, which is instrumental to sound pest management decisions, derives from accurate knowledge of pest dispersion. Results with the different dispersion indices used in this study varied probably on account of insect spatial behaviour's dependence on pest density which itself varies from one cropping season to another (Darbemamieh et al., 2011). The simplest but most unsuitable index was the variance-to-mean ratio (Taylor, 1984). Certain data sets fitted Taylor's regression model better than Iwao's model while others sets fitted Iwao's model better than Taylor's. Mollet et al. (1984) had aptly recommended the use and comparison of different indices to guide decision making.

A rich and diverse species of arthropods colonize watermelon but only a small fraction requires population management interventions. For these, the general clustered dispersion observed in the limited-scale experiment conducted needs to be verified in a larger watermelon production system in order to develop appropriate pest sampling protocol to guide pest management decisions.

Table 5. Population density ($m \pm SE$)/5m-row and variance to mean ratio (S^2/m) of dominant arthropods collected on early-sown watermelon at Wukari in 2016 cropping season.

Species	Seedling Stage		Vegetative stage		Flowering stage		Fruting stage	
	$m \pm SE$	S^2/m	$m \pm SE$	S^2/m	$m \pm SE$	S^2/m	$m \pm SE$	S^2/m
Pest								
<i>A. africana</i>	4.75±0.97	3.985	6.43±0.81	4.110	8.27±0.74	4.041	1.88±0.39	4.744
<i>A. gossypii</i>	-	-	1.18±0.27	2.439	0.95±0.18	2.263	0.62±0.14	1.932
<i>A. nigripennis</i>	4.75±0.98	4.008	6.98±0.87	4.345	9.55±0.88	4.836	4.42±0.58	4.623
<i>A. transversa</i>	2.35±0.58	2.835	5.50±0.77	4.336	8.32±0.68	3.347	3.47±0.53	4.777
<i>B. cucurbitae</i>	-	-	0.30±0.14	2.770	2.47±0.22	1.187	0.62±0.17	2.895
<i>B. tabaci</i>	0.95±0.28	1.600	0.98±0.23	2.171	0.70±0.17	2.484	0.45±0.13	2.442
<i>E. chrysomelina</i>	2.00±0.37	1.370	3.13±0.30	1.135	4.65±0.46	2.682	1.32±0.25	2.923
<i>M. nigeriae</i>	3.45±0.77	3.400	6.30±0.75	3.534	9.58±0.57	2.043	2.48±0.41	4.012
Beneficials								
<i>A. mellifera</i>	-	-	1.43±0.39	4.422	4.12±0.41	2.454	1.07±0.25	3.769
<i>Camponotus</i> sp.	0.10±0.06	0.950	0.53±0.17	2.246	1.25±0.23	2.458	0.17±0.05	1.306
<i>Crematogaster</i> sp.	0.55±0.21	1.618	0.50±0.16	2.052	0.87±0.19	2.707	0.45±0.14	2.669
<i>C. niger</i>	-	-	0.70±0.20	2.433	1.40±0.22	2.209	0.73±0.16	2.362
<i>C. sulphurea</i>	-	-	1.28±0.31	3.005	3.53±0.31	1.608	1.13±0.24	3.164
<i>Pheidole</i> sp.	0.80±0.24	1.525	1.33±0.27	2.183	2.80±0.34	2.419	1.47±0.23	2.216
<i>R. nitidulus</i>	-	-	0.60±0.21	2.975	1.78±0.23	1.830	0.52±0.15	2.823
Spiders	0.25±0.12	1.212	0.60±0.16	1.863	0.32±0.11	2.278	0.63±0.14	1.989

Table 6. Population density ($m \pm SE$)/5m-row and variance to mean ratio (S^2/m) of dominant arthropods collected on late-sown watermelon at Wukari in 2016 cropping season.

Species	Seedling Stage		Vegetative stage		Flowering stage		Fruting stage	
	$m \pm SE$	S^2/m	$m \pm SE$	S^2/m	$m \pm SE$	S^2/m	$m \pm SE$	S^2/m
Pest								
<i>A. africana</i>	1.05±0.37	2.648	3.25±0.73	6.575	5.08±0.62	4.606	1.63±0.36	4.779
<i>A. gossypii</i>	-	-	0.65±0.23	3.198	3.73±0.52	4.379	2.70±0.38	3.242
<i>A. nigripennis</i>	0.45±0.24	2.684	4.43±0.62	3.460	9.70±0.62	2.360	3.58±0.61	6.262
<i>A. transversa</i>	1.10±0.39	2.765	3.30±0.55	3.655	5.55±0.54	3.185	1.63±0.30	3.389
<i>B. cucurbitae</i>	-	-	0.80±0.24	3.090	1.78±0.27	2.458	0.77±0.21	3.449
<i>B. tabaci</i>	-	-	0.58±0.26	4.853	2.90±0.39	3.152	2.45±0.32	2.538
<i>E. chrysomelina</i>	0.45±0.25	2.917	1.28±0.28	2.444	1.63±0.25	2.474	1.55±0.23	1.977
<i>H. armigera</i>	-	-	0.60±0.23	3.573	2.33±0.44	4.883	1.95±0.34	3.675
<i>M. nigeriae</i>	1.06±0.38	2.657	4.12±0.63	3.886	7.42±0.60	2.943	1.57±0.34	4.542
Beneficials								
<i>A. mellifera</i>	-	-	0.33±0.23	6.588	5.37±0.60	3.958	1.17±0.31	4.988
<i>Camponotus</i> sp.	0.75±0.28	2.228	1.30±0.34	3.636	0.92±0.23	3.622	0.45±0.14	2.820
<i>Crematogaster</i> sp.	1.00±0.22	1.053	1.73±0.36	2.964	1.13±0.24	3.073	0.23±0.09	1.969
<i>C. niger</i>	-	-	1.23±0.34	3.689	2.07±0.26	1.963	0.27±0.09	1.992
<i>C. sulphurea</i>	0.60±0.21	1.473	1.15±0.25	2.120	2.77±0.25	1.400	0.65±0.16	2.389
<i>Pheidole</i> sp.	1.90±0.42	1.878	3.30±0.47	2.660	3.42±0.40	2.739	1.28±0.21	2.041
<i>R. nitidulus</i>	-	-	0.70±0.30	5.290	1.53±0.27	2.934	0.80±0.21	3.593
Spiders	0.20±0.11	1.370	0.40±0.16	2.667	0.73±0.19	3.244	0.25±0.11	2.932

Table 7. Comparison of dispersion of dominant arthropods collected on early-sown watermelon at Wukari in 2016 cropping season using Taylor's power law and Iwao's regression model.

Species	Taylor's power law				Iwao's patchiness regression			
	A	b^1	SE_b	R^2	α	β^1	SE_β	R^2
Pest								
<i>A. africana</i>	0.461	1.170	0.162	0.882***	2.294	1.114	0.143	0.897***
<i>A. gossypii</i>	0.188	0.981	0.236	0.712**	0.528	1.170	0.348	0.617*
<i>A. nigipennis</i>	0.103	1.605	0.171	0.926***	0.353	1.383	0.104	0.962***
<i>A. transversa</i>	0.239	1.346	0.121	0.942***	0.708	1.251	0.091	0.964***
<i>B. cucurbitae</i>	0.218	0.627	0.153	0.707**	1.143	0.725	0.286	0.478*
<i>B. tabaci</i>	0.276	1.145	0.148	0.896***	0.876	1.134	0.496	0.428 ^{NS}
<i>E. chrysomelina</i>	0.345	0.766	0.232	0.609*	1.416	0.849	0.148	0.824**
<i>M. nigeriae</i>	0.143	1.254	0.222	0.821**	1.199	1.022	0.092	0.947***
Beneficials								
<i>A. mellifera</i>	0.284	1.243	0.235	0.800*	1.005	1.219	0.215	0.821**
<i>Camponotus</i> sp.	0.222	1.116	0.158	0.877***	0.163	2.233	0.391	0.823**
<i>Crematogaster</i> sp.	0.465	1.420	0.089	0.973***	0.405	2.298	0.581	0.691**
<i>C. niger</i>	0.312	1.106	0.322	0.628*	0.605	1.611	0.440	0.657**
<i>C. sulphurea</i>	0.309	0.898	0.247	0.649**	1.211	0.924	0.254	0.654**
<i>Pheidole</i> sp.	0.231	1.214	0.099	0.956***	0.672	1.125	0.095	0.953***
<i>R. nitidulus</i>	0.232	0.771	0.382	0.368 ^{NS}	0.562	1.261	0.311	0.701**
Spiders	0.380	1.406	0.227	0.845***	-0.273	2.927	0.825	0.643**

¹ NS = > 0.05, * = ≤ 0.05, ** = ≤ 0.01, *** = ≤ 0.001

Table 8. Comparison of dispersion of dominant arthropods collected on late-sown watermelon at Wukari in 2016 cropping season using Taylor's power law and Iwao's regression model.

Species	Taylor's power law				Iwao's patchiness regression			
	A	b^1	SE_b	R^2	α	β^1	SE_β	R^2
Pest								
<i>A. africana</i>	0.433	1.371	0.091	0.970***	1.023	1.542	0.235	0.860***
<i>A. gossypii</i>	0.310	1.315	0.116	0.948***	1.374	1.161	0.135	0.913***
<i>A. nigipennis</i>	0.413	0.918	0.090	0.936***	1.659	0.961	0.056	0.977***
<i>A. transversa</i>	0.459	0.979	0.108	0.921***	2.022	0.966	0.166	0.908***
<i>B. cucurbitae</i>	0.064	2.160	0.319	0.868***	0.165	1.711	0.206	0.907***
<i>B. tabaci</i>	0.202	1.475	0.375	0.689**	0.794	1.347	0.313	0.726**
<i>E. chrysomelina</i>	0.363	0.959	0.158	0.841***	1.336	0.994	0.350	0.535*
<i>H. armigera</i>	0.281	1.753	0.399	0.734**	1.026	1.764	0.500	0.640*
<i>M. nigeriae</i>	0.299	1.150	0.190	0.840**	1.437	1.028	0.116	0.919***

Table 8. Continued

Beneficials								
<i>A. mellifera</i>	0.325	1.366	0.313	0.732**	1.417	1.350	0.259	0.796**
<i>Camponotus</i> sp.	0.489	1.405	0.081	0.977***	0.616	2.364	0.506	0.757***
<i>Crematogaster</i> sp.	0.260	1.219	0.101	0.954***	0.108	1.713	0.206	0.908***
<i>C. niger</i>	0.239	1.065	0.251	0.720**	0.540	1.383	0.283	0.773**
<i>C. sulphurea</i>	0.195	1.071	0.066	0.974***	0.616	0.985	0.120	0.906***
<i>Pheidole</i> sp.	0.253	1.306	0.195	0.855***	0.870	1.226	0.188	0.859***
<i>R. nitidulus</i>	0.415	0.695	0.384	0.319 ^{NS}	1.802	1.309	0.876	0.242 ^{NS}
Spiders	0.628	1.611	0.087	0.980***	0.223	3.778	0.800	0.761**

¹ NS = > 0.05, * = ≤ 0.05, ** = ≤ 0.01, *** = ≤ 0.001

Figure 3. Weekly fluctuations in density of common beneficial arthropods collected on watermelon at Wukari in 2016 cropping season. A) early-sown crop. B) late-sown crop.

Acknowledgments

The assistance of Mr. Ishaku Musa of the Insect Museum Centre of Ahmadu Bello University Zaria, Nigeria in painstakingly using his time and expertise in identifying most of the insects to species level is acknowledged. Many thanks to Mr. Ahmed Mohammed of the Research Farm of the Faculty of Agriculture and Life Sciences, Federal University Wukari and Mr. Igbalagh Christopher for their support during the fieldwork. Sincere thanks also to Mr. Ogunmola Adeniyi of the Statistics Department of Federal University Wukari for support in statistical analyses.

Conflict of Interests

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

References

- Adja, N.H., Danho, M., Alabi, T.A.F., Zimmer, J.Y., Francis, F., Gnago, A.J., Kouassi, K.P., Zoro, I.A. & Baudoin, J.P. (2016) Identification and Impact of Insects Feeding on the Stored Seeds of *Lagenaria siceraria* Molina (Standl. 1930) and *Citrullus lanatus* Thunb (Matsum & Nakai, 1916), two Oilseed Cucurbits of the Ivory Coast. *American Journal of Research Communication*, 4 (2), 104-132.
- Ajayi, F.A., Okrikata, E. & Allahnana, A.M. (2018) Diversity and Abundance of Insects in and Around Faculty of Agriculture, Shabu-Lafia Campus of Nasarawa State University, Nigeria. *International Journal of Applied Research and Technology*, 7 (4), 22-29.
- Ajewole, O.C. (2015) Income and Factor Analysis of Watermelon in Ekiti State, Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 6 (2), 67-72.
- Alao, F.O. & Adebayo T.A. (2015) Comparative Efficacy of *Tephrosia vogelii* and *Moringa oleifera* against Insect Pests of Watermelon. *International Letters of Natural Sciences*, 35, 71-78.
- <https://doi.org/10.18052/www.scipress.com/ILNS.35.71>
- Alao, F.O., Adebayo T.A. & Olaniran O.A. (2016) Population Density of Insect Pests Associated with Watermelon (*Citrullus lanatus* Thunb) in Southern Guinea Savanna Zone, Ogbomoso. *Journal of Entomology and Zoology Studies*, 4 (4), 257-260.
- Arbab, A. & Bakry, M.M.S. (2016) Spatial Distribution and Minimum Sample Size for Monitoring of *Parlatoria* Date scale insect, *Parlatoria blanchardi* (Targioni: Tozzetti) (Hemiptera: Diaspididae) on Date palm trees. *Agricultural Research and Technology Journal*, 2 (3), 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.19080./ARTOAJ.2016.02.555590>
- Bamaiyi, L.J. Alao, S.E.L. & Amans, E. (2010) Optimum Sprays Required for Insect Pests Management on Rainfed Watermelon. *Horticultural Crop Research Programme, Cropping Scheme Reports*, 23-24 February, Zaria, Nigeria. Institute of Agricultural Research, Ahmadu Bello University, pp. 33-35.
- Brook, A.J., Woodcock, D.A., Sinka, M. & Vanbergen, A.J. (2008) Experimental Verification of Suction Sampler Capture Efficiency in Grasslands of Differing Vegetation height and Structure. *Journal of Applied Ecology*, 45, 1357-1363. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2664.2008.01530.x>
- Burabai, W., Etekpe, G.W. Ambah, B. & Angaye, P.E. (2011) Combination of Garlic Extract and some Organophosphate Insecticides in Controlling Thrips (*Thrips palmi*) in Watermelon. *International Journal of Applied Science and Engineering*, 9 (1), 19-23. [https://doi.org/10.6703/IJASE.2011.9\(1\).19](https://doi.org/10.6703/IJASE.2011.9(1).19)
- Darbemamieh, M., Fathipour, Y. & Kamali, K. (2011) Population Abundance and Seasonal Activity of *Zetzellia pourmirzai* (Acari: Stigmaeidae) and its Preys *Cenopalpus irani* and *Bryobia rubrioculus* (Acari: Tetranychidae) in sprayed apple orchards of Kermanshah, Iran. *Journal of Agricultural Science and Technology*, 13, 143-154.

- El Keroumi, A., Naamani, K., Dahbi, A., Luque, I., Carvajal, A., Cerda, X. & Boulay, R. (2010) Effect of Ant Predation and Abiotic Factors on the Mortality of Medfly Larvae, *Ceratitis capitata*, in the Argan Forest of Western Morocco. *Biocontrol Science and Technology*, 20, 751–762.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/09583151003734651>
- Gess, S.K. & Gess, F.W. (2014) *Wasps and Bees in Southern Africa*. SANBI Biodiversity Series 24. South African National Biodiversity Institute, Pretoria, 320 pp.
- Gibson, C.W.D., Hambler, C. & Brown, V.K. (1992) Changes in Spider (Araneae) Assemblages in Relation to Succession and Grazing Management. *Journal of Applied Ecology*, 29, 132–142.
<https://doi.org/10.2307/2404356>
- Gichimu, B.M., Owuor, B.O. & Dida, M.M. (2008) Assessment of Four Commercial Watermelon Cultivars and One Local Landrace for their Response to Naturally Occurring Disease, Pests and Non-Pathogenic Disorders in Sub-Humid Tropical Conditions. *Journal of Agricultural and Biological Science*, 3 (5&6), 32.
- Goreta, S., Perica, S., Dumicic, D., Bucan, L. & Zanic, K. (2005) Growth and Yield of Watermelon on Polyethylene Mulch with Different Spacings and Nitrogen Rates. *American Journal of Horticultural Science*, 40 (2), 366–369.
- Grootaert, P., Pollet, M., Dekoninck, W. & Van Achterberg, C. (2010) Sampling Insects: General Techniques, Strategies and Remarks. In: Eymann, J., Degreef, J., Häuser, J. Monje, C., Samyn, Y. and Vanden Spiegel, D. (eds.) *Manual on Field Recording Techniques and Protocols for All Taxa Biodiversity Inventories and Monitoring*. Abc Taxa, Belgium, pp. 337–399.
- Hammer, O., Harper, D.A.T. & Ryan, P.D. (2001) *PAST: Paleontological Statistics Software Package for Education and Data Analysis*. *Palaeontologia Electronica*, 49 pp.
- Humphries, C.J., Williams, P.H. & Vane-Wright, R.I. (1995) Measuring Biodiversity Value for Conservation. *Annual Review Ecology*, 26, 93–111.
<https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.es.26.110195.000521>
- Iwao, S. & Kuno, E. (1968) Use of the regression of mean crowding on mean density for estimating sample size and the transformation of data for the analysis of variance. *Research on Population Ecology*, 10, 210–214.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02510873>
- Khaing, O., Hormchan P., Jamornmarn S. & Wongpiyasatid W. (2002) Spatial Dispersion and Optimum Sample Size for Cotton Bollworm, *Helicoverpa armigera* (Hubner) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) Larvae on Cotton. *Kasetsart Journal of Natural Science*, 36, 235–241.
- Koul, O. (2008) Phytochemicals and Insect Control: An Antifeedant Approach. *Critical Review of Plant Science*, 27, 1–24.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/07352680802053908>
- Kumar, R. (1984) *Insect Pest Control with Special Reference to African Agriculture*. Edward Arnold Publisher Ltd., London.
- Lima, C.H.O., Sarmiento, R.A., Rosado, J.F., Silveira, M.C.A.C., Santos, G.R., Pedro Neto, M., Erasmo, E.A.L., Nascimento, I. R., & Picanço, M.C. (2014) Efficiency and Economic Feasibility of Pest Control Systems in Watermelon Cropping. *Journal of Economic Entomology*, 107 (3), 1118–1126.
<https://doi.org/10.1603/EC13512>
- Lloyd, M. (1967) Mean crowding. *Journal of Animal Ecology*, 36, 1–30.
<https://doi.org/10.2307/3012>
- Malik, U., Sadiq, I. A., Adamu, R.S., Ahmed, I. A. Jibrin, D.M. & Yakubu, M. (2015) Effect of Planting Dates and Fruitflies (*Bactrocera* spp.) Infestation on Yield of Wet Watermelon (*Citrullus lanatus* Thunb.) in Samaru, Zaria. *Journal of Biopesticides and Agriculture*, 1, 40–45.
- Merrett, P. (1983) Spiders Collected by Pitfall Trapping and Vacuum Sampling in Four Stands of Dorset Heathland Representing Different Growth Phases of Heather. *Bulletin of British Arachnological Society*, 6 (1), 14–22.

- McCravy, K.W. (2018) A Review of Sampling and Monitoring Methods for Beneficial Arthropods in Agroecosystems. *Insects*, 9, 170-197.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/insects9040170>
- Mirab-balou, M., Mahmoudi, M. & Tong, X. (2017) Diversity of Thrips Species (Thysanoptera) in Fruit Orchards in Qazvin province, Northwestern Iran. *Journal of Crop Protection*, 6 (3), 363-373.
- Mollet, J., Trumble, J.T. & Sevacherian, V. (1984) Comparison of Dispersion Indices for *Tetranychus cinnabarinus* (Boisduval) (Acari: Tetranychidae) Population in Cotton. *Environmental Entomology*, 13 (6), 1511-1514.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/ee/13.6.1511>
- Mommertz, S., Schauer, C., Koster, N., Lang, A. & Filser, J. (1996) A Comparison of D-vac Suction, Fenced and Unfenced Pitfall Trap Sampling of Epigeal Arthropods in Agro-Ecosystems. *Annales Zoologici Fennici*, 33, 117-124.
- Mrosso, F., Mwatawala, M. & Rwegasira, G. (2013) Functional Responses of *Cheilomenes propingua*, *C. lunata* and *C. sulphurea* (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae) to Predation on *Aphis gossypii* (Homoptera: Aphididae) in Eastern Tanzania. *Journal of Entomology*, 10 (2), 76-85.
<https://doi.org/10.3923/je.2013.76.85>
- Myers, J.H. (1978) Selecting a measure of dispersion. *Environmental Entomology*, 7, 619-621.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/ee/7.5.619>
- Ogbeibu, A.E. (2014) *Biostatistics: A Practical Approach to Research and Data Handling*. Mindex Publishing Ltd., Benin, Nigeria. 285 pp.
- Ogunlana, M.O. (1996) Insect Pests of Watermelon *Citrullus lanatus* in Samaru Zaria. Research Programmes Reports (1995 - 1996) of Institute of Agricultural Research, Ahmadu Bello University Zaria. pp. 171-172.
- Okrikata, E. & Ogunwolu, E.O. (2017) Farmers' Perceptions on Arthropod Pests of Watermelon and their Management Practices in the Nigerian Southern Guinea Savanna. *International Journal of Agricultural Research*, 12 (4), 146-155.
<https://doi.org/10.3923/ijar.2017.146.155>
- Okrikata, E., Ogunwolu E.O. and Ukwela, M.U. (2019) Efficiency and Economic Viability of Neem Seed Oil Emulsion and Cyperdiforce® Insecticides in Watermelon Production within the Nigerian Southern Guinea Savanna Zone. *Journal of Crop Protection*, 8 (1), 81-101.
- Oliveira, R.F., Ameida, L.C. & Souza, D.R. (2012) Ant Diversity (Hymenoptera: Formicidae) and Predation by Ants on the Different Stages of Sugarcane Borer Life Cycle, *Diatraea saccharalis* (Lepidoptera: Crambidae). *European Journal of Entomology*, 109, 381-387.
<https://doi.org/10.14411/eje.2012.049>
- Pedigo, L.P. & Buntin, G.D. (1994) *Handbook of Sampling Methods for Arthropods in Agriculture*. CRC Press, Boca Raton, Florida. 736 pp.
- Perkins-Veazie, P. & Collins, J.K. (2004) Flesh Quality and Lycopene Stability of Fresh-cut Watermelon. *Postharvest Biology and Technology*, 31, 159-166.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.postharvbio.2003.08.005>
- Richard, F.J., Fabre, A. & Dejean, A. (2001) Predatory Behavior in Dominant Arboreal Ant Species: The Case of *Crematogaster* sp. (Hymenoptera: Formicidae). *Journal of Insect Behaviour*, 14, 271-282.
<https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1007845929801>
- Riechert, S.W. & Lawrence, K. (1997) Test for Predation Effects Versus Multiple Species of Generalist Predators: Spiders and their Insect Prey. *Entomologia et Applicata*, 84, 147-155.
<https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1570-7458.1997.00209.x>
- Sabo, M.U., Wailare, M.A., Aliyu, M., Jari, S. & Shuaibu, Y.M. (2013) Effect of NPK Fertilizer and Spacing on growth and yield of watermelon (*Citrullus lanatus* L.) in Kaltungo Local Government Area of Gombe State, Nigeria. *Scholarly Journal of Agricultural Science*, 3 (8), 325-330.

- Sevacherian, V. & Stern, V.M. (1972) Spatial Distribution Patterns of *Lygus* Bugs in California Cotton Fields. *Environmental Entomology*, 21, 996–1001.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/ee/1.6.695>
- Sisk, T.D., Launner, A.E., Switky, K.R. & Ehrlich, P.R. (1994) Identifying Extinction Threats: Global Analysis of the Distribution of Biodiversity and the Expansion of the Human Enterprise. *Bioscience*, 44, 592–604.
- Soemargono, A., Hasyim, M.A. & Istianto, M. (2011) Spatial Distribution Pattern of Fruit Fly, *Bactrocera dorsalis* Complex (Diptera: Tephritidae) in Mango Orchard. *Agrivita*, 33 (3), 207–213.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.17503/agrivita.v33i3.69>
- Southwood, T.R.E. (1978) *Ecological methods with particular reference to the study of insect populations*. 2nd Ed. Chapman and Hall, London. pp. 524.
- Souza, C.R., Sarmiento, R.A., Venzon, M., Barros, E.C., Santos, G.R. & Chaves, C.C. (2012) Impact of Insecticides on Non-target Arthropods in Watermelon Crop. *Ciências Agrárias*, 33 (5), 1789–1802.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.5433/1679-0359.2012v33n5p1789>
- Standen, V. (2000) The Adequacies of Collecting Techniques for Estimating Species Richness of Grassland Invertebrates. *Journal of Applied Ecology*, 37 (5), 884–893.
<https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-2664.2000.00532.x>
- Steffy, K.L. (1979) Spatial Dispersion and Population Estimation of Northern and Western Corn Rootworm Adults in Iowa Cornfields. Dissertation for Doctor of Philosophy, Department of Entomology, Iowa State University.
<https://doi.org/10.31274/rtd-180813-5618>
- Subramanian, K. & Kitherian, S. (2012) Survey of Reduviids in Cotton Agro-Ecosystem of Tamil-Nadu, India. *Middle-East Journal of Scientific Research*, 12 (9), 1216–1223.
<https://doi.org/10.5829/idosi.mejsr.2012.12.9.1695>
- Taylor, L.R. (1984) Assessing and Interpreting the Spatial Distribution of Insect Populations. *Annual Review of Entomology*, 29, 321–357.
<https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.en.29.010184.001541>
- Tom, H. & Kaippallil, J.D. (2016) A Preliminary Study on the Diversity of Coleopterans in a Rural Area in Changanacherry, Kerala. *Journal of Entomology and Zoology Studies*, 4 (5), 297–300.
- Umeozor, O.C. (1998) Evaluation of Furadan as a Substitute for Aldrin in the Control of Yam Tuber Beetles, *Heteroligus meles* Billb and *H. appius* Burn. (Coleoptera: Dynastidae). *Nigerian Journal of Entomology*, 15, 100–106.
- Wardhaugh, C.W., Stork, N.E. & Edward, W. (2012) Feeding Guild Structure of Beetles on Australian Tropical Rainforest Trees Reflects Microhabitat Resource Availability. *Journal of Animal Ecology*, 81, 1086–1094.

تنوع، توزیع زمانی و مکانی بندپایان مرتبط با هندوانه در منطقه ساوانای جنوبی نیجریه

اوکریکاتا امانوئل^{۱*}، اوگون ولو امانوئل اولودل^۲ و اوکولا ماندی اونابون^۲

۱ گروه علوم زیستی، دانشگاه فدرال ووکاری، ایالت تارا، نیجریه.

۲ گروه حفاظت از محصول و محیط زیست، دانشگاه فدرال کشاورزی، مکوردی، ایالت بنو، نیجریه.

* پست الکترونیکی نویسنده مسئول مکاتبه: eokrikata@gmail.com

تاریخ دریافت: ۰۵ بهمن ۱۳۹۷، تاریخ پذیرش: ۱۱ اسفند ۱۳۹۷، تاریخ انتشار: ۲۰ اسفند ۱۳۹۷

چکیده: نمونه‌های بندپایان مرتبط با هندوانه ابتدا و انتهای فصل در سال ۲۰۱۶ با استفاده از دستگاه نمونه‌بردار مکنده جمع‌آوری شدند. نمونه‌برداری در طول ۵ متر از ردیف‌های میانی ۲۰ کرت آزمایشی واقع در مزرعه تحقیقاتی دانشگاه فدرال وکاری انجام شد. نمونه‌ها بر اساس شکل ظاهری، نوع تغذیه تقسیم بندی شدند. تعیین گونه غالب بر اساس فراوانی نسبی (RA) و فراوانی حضور (FO) انجام شد. شاخص تنوع گونه‌های مختلف نیز محاسبه شد. نمونه‌های جمع‌آوری شده بر اساس الگوی ابتدا و انتهای فصل بر اساس شاخص مشابهت Jaccard (C_j) مقایسه شدند. الگوی توزیع مکانی بندپایان غالب با استفاده از قانونی نمایی تیلور و شاخص رگرسیون آیوانو، تعیین شدند. نتایج بدست آمده نشان داد که جمع‌آوری انجام شده روی هر دو محصول مشابه بودند (C_j= 0.83). تعداد کل ۱۴۴۶۶ نمونه متعلق به یک راسته از عنکبوتیان در رده عنکبوت‌ماندها و ۶۴ گونه در ۴۱ خانواده و ۸ راسته از رده شش‌پایان جمع‌آوری شدند. اطلاعات جمع‌آوری شده نشان دهندهٔ بالا بودن نسبی تنوع گونه‌ای (H = 2.8-3.0) و غنای گونه‌ای (R = 6.0-7.2) بود، اما شاخص یکنواختی کم بود (E = 0.26-0.39). در بین حشرات راسته سخت‌بال‌پوشان (۲۲ گونه) سوسک‌های خانواده Chrysomellidae غالب بودند و پس از آنها حشرات راسته بال‌غشاییان، عموماً شامل مورچه‌ها قرار داشتند. بندپایان غالب (RA ≥ 1.0 و FO ≥ 25.0%) شامل *Asbecesta* *Philanthus triangulum* *Aulacophora africana nigripennis* (پارازیتوئید زنبورهای گرده‌افشان)، *Pheidole* sp.، *Camponotus* sp.، *Rhynocoris nitidulus* و عنکبوت‌ها بودند. اکثر بندپایان غالب دارای توزیع فضایی تجمعی بودند. توزیع بر اساس نحوه و زمان کشت متغیر بود. تنها در مورد ۲۷/۳ درصد از طیف متنوع بندپایان مرتبط با مزرعه هندوانه در وکاری، نیاز به اجرای برنامه‌های مدیریتی بوده و حضور آنها در مناطق تولید با حجم زیاد هندوانه تایید شده است.

واژگان کلیدی: شاخص یکنواختی بوزاس و گیسون، شاخص رگرسیون آیوانو، شاخص شانون - وینر، قانون نمایی تیلور، نسبت واریانس به میانگین.